

SafeMut simulation (WES)

Allele fraction type

- Reference truth
- Real variant
- Simulated variant

Batch

- A 1
- B 2
- C 3
- D 4
- E 5
- F 6

Allele fraction (AF)

log10(depth)

c.1988_2002del

c.886_887del

c.9524_9540del

Mutation

CNT